

FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF Z-PIN REINFORCED DELAMINATION

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SUMMARY

This paper presents our previous and current studies on the fatigue performance of z-pin reinforcement. Z-pin pullout tests under cyclic load were used to study the interfacial bonding and friction degradation. Double-Cantilever Beam (DCB) Mode I delamination tests under cyclic loads were performed to examine crack growth and failure mechanism of z-pinned DCB.

Keywords: Z-Pin Reinforcement; Fatigue; Pullout; Mode I Delamination

INTRODUCTION

Z-pin reinforcements in laminated composites are now widely considered as successful methods to increase the fracture resistance of composite laminates against interlaminar delamination. Z-pins are thin fibrous composite or metallic rods that have high axial stiffness and strength; and they are embedded through prepreg laminates to increase the strength of the composite in the thickness direction. The improvement of delamination toughness is dependent on the volume content, size and mechanical properties of the pins. Experimental and numerical evaluations on the effects of z-pinning on the delamination resistance, in-plane strength and interlaminar buckling were performed over the last 6 years [1-7].

Z-pins increase the delamination toughness by a crack-wake bridging mechanism that involves them spanning across the crack faces so as to reduce the driving force for delamination crack growth. The development of an accurate model of z-pin bridging force is very important for a full analysis of the toughening and failure mechanisms of z-pin reinforced laminates and it cannot be achieved without experimental support. Dai *et al.* [8] conducted an experimental study using a multi-pin pull-out (mode I) test on a

carbon/epoxy laminate under monotonic loading as shown in Figure 1(a). The pull-out curve measured in this test is shown schematically in Figure 1(b). The curve shows three stages in the bridging process; and in order these are: elastic stretching of the pins, debonding of the pins, and pull-out of the debonded pins that involves frictional sliding.

Figure 1 (a) Experimental configuration for z-pin pullout tests; and (b) an illustration of force-displacement curve of a typical pullout test.

In many structural applications composite materials must withstand cyclic or variable loads other than static loads. In-plane tensile and compression fatigue properties and failure mechanisms of z-pinned composite laminates were studied in [9-10]. However, the key function of z-pinning is to provide bridging or closing forces to the interlaminar crack against delamination. A more critical requirement before wide acceptance of this new technique is to characterize the bridging mechanics of z-pins and their effect on the delamination growth under fatigue loading. Although this is recognized as important, little research has been performed in this direction.

In this paper, we present a systematic analysis on the z-pin reinforcement under a cyclic load. Based on our previous studies on z-pin pullout and current work on z-pinned DCB Mode I delamination, the degradation of the z-pin bridging force, delamination growth rate and the failure mechanism are discussed in detail. Numerical simulation of Mode I z-pinned DCB delamination will also be presented.

BRIDGING FORCE DEGRADATION UNDER CYCLIC LOAD

The z-pinned laminate specimens used to study the fatigue bridging properties were made using carbon/epoxy prepreg (HexPly® 914 supplied by Hexcel Composites). The prepreg stack was de-bulked by vacuum bagging and then reinforced using pultruded carbon/bismaleimide z-pins manufactured by Axtex Inc (Waltham, MA). The z-pins were driven into the prepreg using a hand-held ultrasonically actuated horn. The laminate specimens were 40 mm long by 20 mm wide, and a 10 mm x 10 mm region in the centre was reinforced with z-pins arranged in a square grid pattern, as shown in

Figure 1(a). After z-pinning, the prepreg was consolidated and cured in an autoclave at an overpressure of 500 kPa and temperature of 115 °C for 0.5 h and then at 750 kPa and 180 °C for 1.0 h. The cured specimens were then bonded to two T-shaped loading tabs. Before fatigue testing, a series of monotonic load tests were performed to measure the static bridging forces. These tests were conducted at a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min using a 1 kN load capacity Instron 5567 machine. Fatigue testing was performed in the displacement control mode by applying a triangular load waveform with a frequency of 0.5 Hz on the specimens. The maximum displacement values (δ_{\max}) applied were 50% or 80% of the debonding displacement (δ_1) measured in the monotonic pull-out test; and the minimum displacement (δ_{\min}) was set at 10% of δ_{\max} (i.e., displacement ratio R=10). The fatigue tests were performed over a specific number of load cycles, and then the specimen was pulled to failure under monotonic loading to measure the residual bridging force. More details of the specimen preparation and testing procedures were given in [11].

The degradation of the friction pull-out force (P_f) due to cyclic loading was also measured. A monotonic increasing load was applied to the specimen until the load dropped due to debonding of the pins to a certain load and corresponding displacement, δ_s . The specimen was then subjected to cyclic maximum and minimum displacements specified by the following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}\delta_{\max} &= \delta_s + 0.5\delta_1 \\ \delta_{\min} &= \delta_s - 0.5\delta_1\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where δ_1 is the displacement when the pins began to debond from the laminates. The reduction in the applied force was measured with increasing number of load cycles to monitor the degradation of the friction load.

Figure 2(a) shows the residual debonding force (P_d/P_{do}) versus number of load cycles. The specimens contained an array of 4 x 4 pins with diameter, $d=0.51$ mm, (Type 4) and were tested at a fatigue displacement ratio (δ_{\max}/δ_1) of 0.5 and 0.8, respectively. It is shown that in both cases, the maximum debonding force decreases with increasing load cycles. However, the degradation rate of the debonding force increases with the displacement ratio due to the high fracture energy applied to the pin/laminates interface.

Figure 2(b) shows the reduction in the friction pull-out force with increasing number of load cycles for three specimens containing an array of 7 x 7 pins ($d=0.28$ mm, Type 2). The friction pull-out force (P_{fs}) and corresponding displacement (δ_s) at which the monotonic test was stopped to begin the fatigue tests for three specimens are shown in Table 1. The frictional force at certain loading cycles (P_f) is normalized by the friction pull-out force under monotonic loading (P_{fs}). Compared to the debonding force (P_d), the frictional pull-out force decreases more rapidly with elapsed load cycles. This suggests that the fatigue-induced damage accumulates more rapidly once the pins have fully debonded, when they are free to slide back and forth against the walls of the hole. This sliding action wears out the surfaces of the pin and the hole.

Based on the experimental results in Figure 2, the degradation models of bridging forces were also developed in [11]. The comparisons between the predicted curves and the

experimental data are shown in Figure 2. The predicted curves were calculated by two power-law degradation functions given below:

$$P_d(\delta_{\max}, N) = P_{d0}(\log N)^{-\beta \delta_{\max} / \delta_1} \quad (2a)$$

$$P_f(\delta_s, N) = P_{f0}(\log N)^{-\beta \delta_s / \delta_1} \quad (2b)$$

Figure 2 (a) Residual debonding force degradation and (b) frictional force degradation with number of cycles.

Table 1 Parameters for frictional force degradation test.

Sample number	P_{f0} (N)	δ_s (mm)
2-1	908	0.665
2-2	736	0.606
2-10	856	0.643

In Eq. (2a) P_{d0} is maximum debonding force under monotonic loading (that is, $N=1$) and β is a coefficient determined by a regression curve-fitting of the degradation of the z-pin bridging force in Figure (2a). In Eq. (2b), P_{f0} is the frictional bridging force for monotonic loading ($N=1$) and δ_s is an initial applied displacement to debond the z-pin from the laminates in the pull-out test. Since the degradation of frictional force is very rapid, we only consider the case of low cycle fatigue, that is, $\log N \leq 4$. In Figure (2b), the ratios of δ_s / δ_1 were taken as, 3, 4.9, 6 and 7 while the ratio of $\delta_s / \delta_1 = 4.9$ was

used to measure the experimental results of frictional bridging force. By applying the above bridging force degradation model to our previous analysis for Mode I z-pinned delamination [3], delamination crack growth under cyclic load can be predicted [11].

MODE I DELAMINATION GROWTH WITH Z-PIN REINFORCEMENT UNDER CYCLIC LOAD

Multi-layered biaxial weft knitted (MBWK) fabric made of E-glass fibre insertion yarns and polyester stitch yarns were cut and two fabrics were stacked together and pinned in the thickness direction. MBWK fabric was supplied by Tianjin Polytechnic University with a thickness about 2 mm. The z-pins were made of carbon fibres CCF3002-3K-41 supplied by Weihai Tuo-Zhan Fibre Co. Ltd. The epoxy matrix E51 was obtained from Shanghai Ju-Xing Chemical Co. Ltd and cured with an amine modified epoxy hardener. The diameters of z-pins ranged from 0.28 to 0.51 mm, among which 0.37 mm and 0.51 mm z-pins were used in this study. The z-pinned fabric preforms were then impregnated with E51 epoxy resin via vacuum bag in the oven. The curing process started with 35 °C for 2h, and then kept 50 °C for 1.5h and lastly 80 °C for 2.5h. Teflon® film was inserted between the fabrics before stacking to get a pre-crack. More details on the materials and sample preparation can be found in [12, 13]. Sample groups, N1, N2 and N3, were prepared with z-pins of 0.37 mm diameter. The distributions of z-pins are shown in Figure 3a, 3b and 3c, respectively. Sample K1 was prepared with the z-pins of 0.51 mm in diameter. The distribution of z-pins in K1 is the same as N1 shown in Figure 3a. To reduce the large grip displacement and resultant bending failure of the DCB, carbon fibre/epoxy laminates of 1 mm thickness with $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/\pm 45^{\circ}]_s$ plies were bonded on both sides. The total thickness of the DCBs was 6.00 ± 0.09 mm. The effect of the reinforcing composite laminate tabs to the toughness was evaluated by Jain *et al* [14].

Figure 3 Sample geometries.

Mode I fatigue delamination tests were performed on a 2 kN capacity MTS 810 testing machine. Test set-up is shown in Figure 4a. The tests were conducted under load control mode. The maximum load was 150 N which was chosen on the basis of static loading and kept the same for all the samples. Testing frequency was 4 Hz. Under this

frequency, the limitation of displacement amplitude of the testing machine is 3.17 mm. However, when the delamination crack was large, the displacement of DCB was large. When the displacement amplitude exceeded the limitation, the machine could not respond properly. Therefore, in the tests, we kept the maximum load constant (150 N) and let the minimum load vary from 0.5~0.7 of the maximum load to coordinate with the machine's response. Crack length was recorded by a Nikon camera COOLPIX S52 as shown in Figure 4b.

Figure 4 (a) Test set-up; and (b) an image of the delamination crack tip.

Figure 5 Crack length *versus* fatigue cycle.

The crack length a and corresponding fatigue cycle N were recorded, as given in Figure 5. The fatigue delamination crack growth rate da/dN was derived from the discrete $a-N$ curve with the B-spline fitting data reduction scheme [12].

Figure 6 Fatigue crack growth rate *versus* crack length.

In Figure 5, the sample without z-pins shows the most rapidly rising trend indicating the highest delamination growth rate, da/dN , which is confirmed in Figure 6. The DCB is fully delaminated in less than 12,500 cycles. Compared to other z-pinned DCB groups, K1, with larger diameter but fewer z-pins, does not show much benefit when the crack length is small. The fatigue life of K1 is even shorter than that of N1 in which the z-pin density is lower. However, when the crack length exceeds 68 mm, the effect of z-pins becomes obvious, see Figure 6. As discussed in our previous studies [8, 16], compared to the small-diameter pins with the same areal density, large-diameter pins have lower bridging force but larger resistance against bending under a high loading rate. When the delamination crack is long, the displacement of DCB is large. The cyclic load of 4 Hz results in a very high loading rate applied to the DCB. The phenomenon shown in this test is consistent with the conclusion obtained from our previous work.

From Figures 5 and 6, it can be seen that the N3 group has the best fatigue performance. Compared to N2 group, which has the same z-pin density, N3 group has a longer fatigue life and the delamination crack grows steadily in most of the pinned area. A plateau is seen in the pinned area in Figure 6. This observation reflects the damage accumulation at the z-pin interface under fatigue. N3 has more z-pins in each column and a larger pin-to-pin distance compared to N2. When the crack tip passes a certain column, the pins in this column can provide a sufficient bridging force to the DCB to shield the pins in the next column from being pulled out. As we show in Figure 2, the bridging force degradation reduces with decreasing applied displacement. Thus, the z-pins in N3 group suffer less interfacial damage before they are fully pulled out.

Further fatigue tests will be conducted on different types of samples and also on Mode II delamination. More details and results will be given in [12].

SIMULATION OF MODE I DELAMINATION GROWTH WITH Z-PIN REINFORCEMENT UNDER CYCLIC LOAD

A mechanics model was developed in [11] to simulate the Mode I delamination growth of z-pinned DCB. There, the bridging force degradation was considered functions of the load cycle and could be calculated by Eq. (2). The fracture energy method is used as the delamination criterion [15]. If the maximum energy release rate is greater than a critical intrinsic toughness of the unpinned DCB, G_{IC} , the delamination propagates. Otherwise, increase fatigue cycles $N=N+\Delta N$. The degradation of the intrinsic toughness of the DCB was assumed to obey the relation given by:

$$G_{IC}(N) = G_{IC}^i e^{-\alpha \log N} \quad (3)$$

where G_{IC}^i denotes the toughness of unpinned DCB under monotonic load ($N=1$). Thus, the delamination propagates, $a=a+\Delta a$, and the propagation rate, $da/dN=\Delta a /N$, can be obtained. More details were given in [11].

Fig. 7 shows the simulation results under load-control mode in which the applied maximum load $P_{max}=0.75P_{cr}$, where P_{cr} is load value at onset of delamination from the pre-crack tip in quasi-static loading. With increment of crack length, the delamination growth rate of the unpinned beam increases, but the z-pinned beam shows a different trend. When the crack reaches the first column of pins, the delamination growth rate starts to decrease and reaches the lowest delamination rates when the crack length is 60 mm which is about the location of the second column of z-pins. Then delamination rate increases slowly before the crack passes through the whole pinned length (i.e., $a=80$ mm). When the crack has passed the last column of pins, the delamination rate merges with the unpinned beam in the end. It is clear that the z-pins can effectively arrest the delamination growth before they are all pulled out. The slight increase in da/dN is due to the degradation in the intrinsic toughness of the DCB. However, in the experimental results shown in Figure 6, stable crack propagation can never reach the last column of z-pin. In most cases, only the first two or three columns can slow down the delamination propagation. The difference between the theoretical prediction and experimental results implies that damages in z-pins before the crack reaches them were not considered in the modelling. Detailed study in the failure mechanism of z-pin reinforcement under fatigue will be a direction of our future study.

Figure 7 also shows the effect of bridging force degradation on fatigue crack growth. If the degradation of bridging forces were not considered in the simulation, delamination growth is slowed down substantially by z-pinning.

Due to the difference in materials, the simulation results of this model cannot match the experimental results quantitatively. A pullout test using the same material system as that used in the fatigue tests is needed to determine the bridging law. However, based on a qualitative comparison of the above studies, we can make the following conclusions:

(a) Z-pinning can efficiently slow down the crack growth rate thereby improving the fatigue life of composites.

(b) Interfacial degradation may decrease the effect of z-pin reinforcement under cyclic load. However, an optimised distribution of z-pins may minimise the interfacial damage accumulation.

(c) Under high frequency fatigue, the bending resistance from z-pins may become more important to the composite beams.

Figure 7 Crack propagation rate *versus* crack length under load-control, z-pin areal density=0.5%.

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